

At: European Association for the History of Medicine and Health 2025 Conference: Health Beyond Medicine (EAHMH 2025 Conference), with the co-operation of Humboldt University, 26-29.08.2025, Berlin, Germany.

Alcoholism as a medical and social problem in Porto in the XIX century: science, morality and social control

Célia Oliveira – Lab2PT/IN2PAST, University of Minho, PT

FCT scholarship ref. 2023.05192.BD. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54499/2023.05192.BD>

BeFRAIL - Porto in Times of Cholera and War: A Bioarchaeological Approach to Human Frailty. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.02398.PTDC>.

Title: Alcoholism as a Medical and Social Problem in Porto in the XIX century: Science, Morality and Social Control

Célia OLIVEIRA^{1,2}

1 Lab2PT – Laboratory of Landscapes, Heritage and Territory (University of Minho, Braga, Portugal)

2 IN2PAST – Associate Laboratory for Research and Innovation in Heritage, Arts, Sustainability and Territory (University of Évora, Portugal)

Abstract: This study aims to analyze the medical and social construction of alcoholism in the city of Porto in the second half of the 19th century, focusing on the intersection between medical discourse and punitive practices. Based on the narratives found in medical periodicals of the time and records of fines for transgressions related to situations of drunkenness and public disorder, the study seeks to understand the duality between the medical discourse—which examines alcohol consumption from the perspective of health, morality, and science—and the legal measures applied to transgressing individuals. It also seeks to find out whether the perception of alcoholism that doctors and legal authorities have built up in an interconnected way has contributed to its medicalization or to the stigma associated with excessive drinking behaviour. It is hoped that this study will contribute to the historical understanding

of the problem of alcoholism, demonstrating the mutual influence between medical knowledge and punitive policies in the consolidation of social control practices.

Keywords: Alcoholism; Medicalization; Social control; Medical discourse; Nineteenth-century Porto.